

Sustainable Coffee Waste Management Through Circular Economy

Shatanik Chakraborty, Tushar Singh, Dhruv Agrawal, Aadil Ahmed Irshath and Anand Prem Rajan*

Department of Biomedical Sciences, School of Bio Sciences and Technology,
Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT), Vellore, Tamil Nadu, India

***Corresponding author**

Dr Anand Prem Rajan

Professor

School of Bio Sciences and Technology (SBST)

Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT)

Vellore – 632014, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract: Coffee is one of the most important agricultural products in the world. Most spent coffee grounds (SCGs), a by-product of brewing coffee, are buried in landfill sites, and their decomposition produces significant greenhouse gases. As coffee production is expected to increase in the future, it is essential to find suitable industrial uses for the by-products and waste generated from the coffee-making process. These materials are renewable and contain valuable nutrients such as carbohydrates, proteins, pectin, and bioactive compounds like polyphenols. Therefore, it is crucial to strike a balance between coffee production and the responsible utilization of its by-products. As the recent warming of the Earth's climate has made it imperative that industries reduce greenhouse gas emissions, the present study investigates the viability of recycling SCGs for use as replacement of paper cups. The study suggests that waste management guidelines should be revised to incorporate life cycle thinking for sustainable resource management in a circular economy. In this paper, we present an overview of utilizing the spent coffee grounds.

Keywords: Spent coffee grounds (SCGs); coffee waste; eco-friendly; waste utilization

Introduction

Coffee – the ubiquitous drink that transcends all political and geographical boundaries, bringing the world's morning warriors and late-night laborers together in a ritual daily sigh of caffeinated relief. The world population drinks over 2.8 billion cups of coffee every day. The UK alone is responsible for 98 million of these cups. With an estimated average of 11 grams of fresh ground coffee going into each cup, around 393,500 tons of ground coffee are brewed every year, resulting in an estimated 250,000 tons of wet coffee grounds waste. But what will happen to all the used coffee grounds once the coffee is poured: Coffee grounds are a by-product of brewing coffee [1]. About 0.91 g of the spent coffee grounds are produced per 1 g of ground coffee. SCG are composed of 12.4% cellulose, 39.1% hemicellulose (3.6% arabinose, 19.07% mannose, 16.43% galactose), 23.9% lignin, 2.29% fat, 17.44% protein, and 60.46% of total dietary fibres. Typically, spent coffee grounds are dumped into general waste and sent to landfill where they decompose and emit methane – a greenhouse gas 25 times more potent than carbon dioxide over a 100-year period, and one of the primary causes of global warming [2]. This level of hazardous waste is catastrophic. Approximately 10 billion paper cups in India are used for coffee every single year, which leads to 4.5 million trees cut down, 3 billion gallons of water going to waste, and enough energy to power 47,000 homes for a year also goes to waste. A recent study by IIT Kharagpur confirmed the presence of contaminated particles in hot liquids served in paper cups due to microplastic degradation. As of 2019, it is estimated that over 15 million tonnes of used coffee grounds are generated annually. Paper cups takes around **20 years** to totally decompose. We have established a circular economy by primarily using coffee grounds, largely considered as waste to build our products [3][4]. We have utilised this undervalued resource to create sustainable products, building a business by tackling the issue of coffee waste management. Coffee grounds, generally dumped in landfills is a major contributor of greenhouse gases and utilising this as our resource is the core strength of our project. Sustainability and creativity have merged to put together what is now our project. We transform this waste to biodegradable cutlery products. Our goal is to make an impact and change people's mindset towards waste.

Goal

Sustainable product development from used up coffee ground would likely be to reduce the environmental impact of coffee production by repurposing waste materials, while also creating useful and eco-friendly products for consumers [5]. This mission would include a commitment to using sustainable and environmentally friendly production methods, as well as promoting awareness about the importance of reducing waste in the coffee industry [6].

Total	151 623
Arabicas	95 204
<i>Colombian Milds</i>	15 779
<i>Other Milds</i>	26 951
<i>Brazilian Naturals</i>	52 474
Robustas	56 419
Africa	16 353
Asia & Oceania	43 110
Mexico & Central America	17 740
South America	74 420

Table 1. Production of coffee in thousand 60 kg bags in 2016 [7].

Figure 1. Detailed process of how coffee grounds are transformed to biodegradable cutlery [8][26].

Collection of Coffee Grounds: The first step is to collect the coffee grounds.

Mixing the Grounds: The coffee grounds are then mixed with other natural materials such as corn-starch, wheat starch, or bamboo fibre to form a dough-like substance [9].

Adding Adhesives: To improve the strength and durability of the cutlery, a natural adhesive such as glycerine or soy protein can be added to the mixture.

Moulding: The mixture is then moulded into the desired shape using moulds or manually shaping it.

Drying: The moulded cutlery is left to dry, either in the sun or in a dehydrator, until it reaches a sturdy consistency.

Finishing: Once the cutlery has dried, it can be sanded down to remove any rough edges or bumps, and then polished to give it a smooth finish.

Packaging: The final product is then packaged for distribution and sale [12].

The 5 Ts of Vision:

- ✓ Fostering a society in which coffee waste is viewed as a resource rather a problem.
- ✓ Inspiring and leading the coffee industry towards circular economy practices, where waste is minimized and resource is maximized.
- ✓ Catalyst for a shift in consumer behaviour towards more sustainable products and practices.
- ✓ Helping to build a more resilient and sustainable future for coffee farmers, processes and communities.
- ✓ Being a role model for other industries on how to turn waste into valuable resources and minimize environmental impact.

Coffee receptacles that modify the tasting experience:

It has been exhibited already that the surface textures of product packaging and serving ware can influence the apparent taste and mouthfeel of different various food varieties and refreshments. The purpose of this study was to see if experts (Q-graders) and casual coffee drinkers' perceptions of specialty coffee's taste and mouthfeel could be affected by coffee cups with different surface textures [17]. A sum of 231 members were tried in one of the three examinations. A preliminary experiment that was carried out at a Russian specialty coffee event found that rubbing a swatch of sandpaper against a cup of coffee influenced the qualities of the coffee's perceived body and aftertaste. The participants in the two primary studies, Experiment 1 for Q-graders, and Experiment 2 for amateurs, evaluated a sample of specialty coffee served in either a smooth or rough ceramic cup. The Q-graders thought the coffee tasted significantly more acidic when it was tasted from the rough cup than the smooth cup. On the other hand, amateurs thought the coffee tasted significantly sweeter when it was tasted from the smooth cup rather than the rough cup. When tasted from the rough cup rather than the smooth one, the aftertaste was significantly dryer, according to both Q-graders and amateurs. None of the experiments had a significant impact on how people perceive their bodies. These findings show that expert and novice coffee drinkers alike are influenced by haptic cues when evaluating basic flavours and mouthfeel characteristics. However, it is essential to create cups that convey some functional and/or perceptual benefit for the coffee drinking experience in addition to innovation [20].

The present study's findings demonstrate for the first time that experts (Q-graders) and casual consumers alike can be significantly affected by "sensation transference" from the haptic feel of cup texture [22]. As a result, the findings of this study lend credence to the idea that the vessel used to drink coffee is an essential component of the multisensory coffee drinking experience [23].

Significance of coffee waste

Coffee waste production is significant for several reasons

Environmental impact: Coffee waste is a significant contributor to environmental pollution. Coffee grounds and wastewater are often dumped in landfills or water bodies, leading to soil and water pollution. In addition, the production of coffee involves the use of pesticides, fertilizers, and energy, which also have environmental implications [24]. **Economic value:** Coffee waste can be recycled and repurposed, creating value for businesses and communities. For example, coffee grounds can be used as a natural fertilizer, animal feed, or even to produce biofuels. Additionally, some companies are exploring the potential for extracting valuable compounds from coffee waste, such as antioxidants and bioactive compounds [25]. **Social impact:** Coffee waste production has a significant impact on the livelihoods of coffee farmers and workers. By reducing waste and increasing the value of coffee production, farmers and workers can improve their incomes and living standards.

Market analysis

Market analysis about coffee waste production involves examining the current and potential market trends, demand, and supply dynamics, and identifying the opportunities and challenges in the market. Here are some key points to consider in a market analysis of coffee waste production [26]:

Market size and growth potential: The market for coffee waste is still relatively small but is expected to grow in the coming years as businesses and communities become more aware of the potential economic and environmental benefits of recycling coffee waste. The growth potential of the market will depend on factors such as government policies, consumer behaviour, and technological innovations [27].

Market segmentation: The market for coffee waste can be segmented into different categories based on the type of waste produced, such as coffee grounds, coffee chaff, or coffee pulp. Each category has different potential uses and value propositions [28].

Competitive landscape: The market for coffee waste is competitive, with several players offering different products and services related to coffee waste recycling. These players include waste management companies, composting facilities, animal feed producers, and biofuel companies [29].

Regulatory environment: Government regulations and policies can have a significant impact on the coffee waste market. For example, incentives and subsidies for recycling coffee waste can encourage businesses to invest in this market [30].

Consumer behaviour: The demand for coffee waste products and services will depend on consumer behaviour, including awareness of the environmental and economic benefits of recycling coffee waste. Consumer preferences for sustainable products and services may also drive demand in this market [31].

Financial Support for Market production

There are several financial support options that you can explore for making products from coffee waste. Here are a few examples:

Government grants: Depending on your location, you may be able to apply for government grants that support sustainable and innovative projects. Look for grants related to waste reduction, circular economy, and sustainable development. You can search for relevant grants on government websites or by contacting your local government offices [32].

Impact investing: Impact investors are individuals or organizations that invest in projects that have a positive social or environmental impact, in addition to generating financial returns. If your coffee waste product aligns with an impact investor's investment criteria, you may be able to secure funding. You can search for impact investors online or through your local business networks [33].

Venture capital: Venture capitalists are investors who provide funding to startups and early-stage companies with high growth potential. If your coffee waste product has a strong business model and growth potential, you may be able to secure venture capital funding. You can search for venture capitalists online or through your local business networks [34][35].

Crowdfunding: Crowdfunding is a method of raising funds from many people through the Internet. You can create a crowdfunding campaign to fund your waste coffee products and promote it through social media and other channels [36][40].

Corporate partnerships: Some companies may be interested in partnering with you to develop and commercialize your coffee waste product. Look for companies that have a sustainability focus or that operate in the same industry as your product.

Several companies utilizing coffee ground waste:

Huskee: Huskee is a company that produces reusable coffee cups and other products made from coffee husk, the discarded outer layer of a coffee bean. They collect the husks from coffee processing factories and use them to create durable and sustainable cups that are designed to last for years.

Kaffeeform: Kaffeeform is a German company that produces coffee cups and saucers made from used coffee grounds. They collect the coffee grounds from cafes and coffee shops, dry and sterilize them, and then combine them with natural resins to create a durable material that can be moulded into various shapes.

Cupffee: Cupffee is a Bulgarian company that produces edible coffee cups made from natural ingredients, including coffee grounds. The cups are designed to be used for hot and cold drinks and can be eaten after use, reducing waste, and providing a unique drinking experience.

Ecoffee Cup: Ecoffee Cup is a UK-based company that produces reusable coffee cups made from bamboo fibre, which is combined with other natural materials, including coffee grounds. The cups are lightweight, durable, and come in various designs and colours.

By utilizing coffee ground waste to make cups, these companies are helping to reduce waste and create sustainable products that can be used and reused for years [42].

Conclusion

Coffee waste can be a valuable resource with great potential for creating various products. Through innovative approaches and sustainable practices, we can transform coffee waste into useful and eco-friendly products, leading to environmental conservation and economic benefits. One significant application of coffee waste is in agriculture. Coffee grounds can serve as a rich source of organic matter, improving soil fertility and enhancing plant growth. They can be used as compost or incorporated into the soil as a natural fertilizer, reducing the reliance on chemical fertilizers and promoting sustainable farming practices. Furthermore, coffee waste can be utilized in the production of biofuels. The high cellulose content in coffee husks and spent coffee grounds makes them suitable for bioenergy production. By converting coffee waste into biofuels such as pellets or briquettes, we can reduce our dependency on fossil fuels and mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. Coffee waste also has potential in the realm of sustainable materials. Researchers have explored the use of coffee grounds in the production of bioplastics, which can be a greener alternative to traditional petroleum-based plastics. These coffee-based bioplastics possess properties like biodegradability and lower environmental impact, making them a promising solution to the global plastic pollution problem. In addition, coffee waste can find application in the cosmetic and personal care industry. Coffee grounds, when incorporated into skincare products, can serve as a natural exfoliant, helping to remove dead skin cells and improve skin texture. The antioxidant properties of coffee waste can also be harnessed in the formulation of anti-aging and skincare products, providing potential benefits to consumers.

However, it is essential to consider the scale and feasibility of coffee waste utilization. While there are promising developments and research in this area, widespread adoption and commercialization of coffee waste-based products may require further investment, technological advancements, and supportive policies. Collaboration between coffee producers, waste management systems, researchers, and industries is crucial to fully harness the potential of coffee waste and maximize its positive impact. In conclusion, coffee waste presents a valuable opportunity to create sustainable and innovative products across various industries. By effectively managing coffee waste and utilizing it in environmentally friendly ways, we can contribute to resource conservation, waste reduction, and a more sustainable future.

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